

SPATIAL PATTERNS OF SOIL ORGANIC CARBON IN WATER-STABLE AGGREGATE FRACTIONS IN CONTINUOUSLY CULTIVATED CROPLANDS ON DIFFERENT PARENT MATERIALS

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Abstract: A study was carried out on soil geo-referenced and sampled at 0-100 cm depth in continuously cultivated croplands to evaluate the potential of various aggregate size fractions (> 2.00, 0.50-1.00, 0.25-0.50, <0.25 mm) to sequester carbon under different parent materials and croplands in southern Nigeria, using geospatial techniques. Soil samples were collected from continuously cultivated croplands with varying parent materials. Results revealed that SOC content had low ($p < 0.05$) concentration in fractions >0.50 mm whereas, higher ($p < 0.05$) concentration was observed in fractions <0.50 mm across the parent materials and croplands. Semi-variogram indicated that SOC in aggregate size fractions was variable. Nugget variance (C_0) range was (0.061- 0.942). Coefficient of determination (R^2) of predicted SOC content were >0.50, which showed a good fit. Low (0.31-0.572) root mean square error (RMSE) showed that theoretical model was adequate patterns of SOC content. It therefore implies that SOC were sequestered majorly in small-sized aggregate (0.25- 0.50 mm), and micro-aggregates (<0.25 mm) across the various arable croplands. These emphasize significance of considering both parent materials and cultural practices in managing SOC in Croplands in Southern Nigeria. Sustainable soil management practices should be encouraged in the study area. This will promote soil aggregation and C sequestration in aggregate size fractions, thereby enhancing soil health and productivity, leading to food security.

Keywords: SOC sequestration, Aggregate Sizes, Parent materials, Croplands, Geospatial techniques

1.0 Introduction

Soil organic carbon (SOC) is an important component of the soil ecosystem, playing a vital role in soil fertility, carbon sequestration, and overall soil health. It is well recognized that the spatial distribution of SOC within the soil profile is highly heterogeneous, influenced by a variety of biotic and abiotic factors such as soil texture, Land use practices, climate and topography (Ibe, 2021). In arable soils, the management practices adapted by farmers, including tillage, crop rotation, and application of organic amendments, can significantly impact the distribution and storage of SOC (Amanze *et al.* 2025). Adequate understanding of SOC distribution in cultivated croplands is essential for implementing effective conservation practices and sustainable management strategies to enhance soil health and food security, while mitigating the effects of climate change (Amanze *et al.*, 2024a). According to Amanze *et al.* (2024b), soil organic carbon plays a pivotal role in soil health, fertility and ecosystem functioning. It is an essential component of the soil that contribute to soil structure, water holding capacity, nutrient availability and overall soil health. Ibe (2025) agreed that spatial distribution and dynamics of SOC in soil aggregates is important for assessing soil

quality, carbon sequestration potential, and sustainable land management practices.

In cultivated soils, SOC is often affected by land management practices such as tillage, cropping system, fertilization, and irrigation (Backlund, 2008; Bird, 2015). Continuous cultivation of agricultural lands can lead to the depletion of SOC, which in turn can impact soil fertility, crop productivity, and ecosystem services. The distribution of SOC in different aggregate fractions is an important indicator of SOC in soil (Garage *et al.*, 2003). Soil aggregates are formed through physical, chemical, and biological processes that result in the aggregation of soil particles into distinct size fractions. In particular, water-stable aggregates are aggregates that are resistant to breakdown when subjected to wetting and drying cycles, making them important for soil structure and carbon sequestration (Xie *et al.* 2012; Olaye *et al.*, 2016).

One of the key aspect of SOC distribution in agricultural soils is it's association with soil aggregates, which are structurally defined units of soil particles held together by organic matter, clay minerals, and other binding agents. Soil aggregates play a crucial role in determining soil physical and chemical properties, including porosity, water retention, and nutrient availability (Igwe and

Obalum, 2013). Among the various aggregate fractions present in the soil, water-stable aggregates are particularly important as they are resistant to mechanical breakdown and water erosion, thus serving as reservoirs for SOC storage and protection against soil degradation (Lal, 2015; Ibe *et al.* 2025).

Amanze *et al.* (2024b) noted that size distribution and stability of soil aggregates are influenced by soil management practices, such as tillage intensity, crop residue management, and soil amendments. Intensive tillage practices, such as plowing and cultivation, can disrupt soil aggregates and accelerate the decomposition of organic matter, leading to a decline in SOC stocks and soil fertility. On the other hand, Ibe *et al.* (2025) reported that conservation tillage practices, such as minimum tillage or no-till, can enhance soil aggregation in stable aggregates. Therefore, characterizing the spatial distribution of SOC within different aggregate fractions can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of various land management practices in enhancing SOC stocks and improving soil quality in cultivated croplands.

In addition to soil management practices, parent material of the soil also plays a significant role in determining the spatial pattern of SOC distribution in agricultural

soils. Different parent materials in the tropical rainforest, such as sandstone, Shale, Coastal plain sands and basement complex or limestone, etc. possess distinct mineralogical and chemical properties that influence soil formation processes, nutrient availability, and microbial activities. Igwe and Obalum (2013) reported that these differences in parent material can result in variations in soil properties, including SOC content, aggregation dynamics, and water retention capacity. Therefore, assessing the spatial distribution of SOC in water-stable aggregate fractions on various parent materials can provide valuable insights into the interactions between soil mineralogy, land use practices, and SOC sequestration in cultivated croplands.

Improved water-stable aggregate fractions in soils are essential for C sequestration. Hence, improvement of water-stable aggregates is a useful strategy for mitigating increase in concentration of atmospheric CO₂ (Bird, 2015). Human activities related to soil management and cultural practices that leads to the breakdown of soil aggregates and/or inhibits aggregate formation, have contributed to the buildup of carbon dioxide (CO₂) to the atmosphere and various degrees of soil degradation (IPCC, 2001; Lal, 2015; Okebalama, 2016). During the past 150 years,

land use and soil ecosystem disturbance were responsible for one third of all human emissions of CO₂ (Shahmir *et al.*, 2017; Meng-Yuh & Shoa, 2014). Land cover removal and inappropriate soil management are responsible for overall soil nutrient depletion and erosion (Olaye *et al.*, 2016; Zachary & James, 2013). Over the next 100 years, global land use system, land cover removal and inappropriate soil management and cultural practices are likely to account for at least 10 percent of overall human caused CO₂ emission and environmental degradation (Baldyga, 2005; Backlund, 2008; EPA, 2008 and IPCC, 2000, 2007). The dominant drivers of current and past land use related emission of CO₂ are the conversion of forest and grassland to crop and pasture land and the depletion of soil carbon, through agricultural tillage system and longterm continuously cultivation of soil. (Ding *et al.*, 2016; Linsier *et al.*, 2013; Onweremadu *et al.*, 2011).

Geospatial techniques, including remote sensing, geographic information systems, (GIS), and spatial analysis, offer powerful tools for mapping and analyzing the spatial distribution of SOC in agricultural soils (Ibe, 2021). These techniques allow for the integration of soil data with environmental factors, such as topography, climate, and land use, to identify patterns and trends in SOC

distribution. By combining field -based soil sampling with geospatial analysis, researchers can develop detailed maps of SOC content in soil aggregates and assess the factors influencing its spatial variability.

Quantification of SOC within aggregates size classes permits evaluation of aggregation under different soil management systems and its contribution to the accumulation and loss of SOM (Sotomayor-Ram'irez *et al.*, 2006; Calero *et al.*, 2008). The relevance of this study is to generate reliable information which is essential for developing techniques of soil/land management systems and for recommendation sequestration for sustainable agriculture and erosion control leading to advancement in food security and consequently, mitigate global warming, using five (5) location in the southern agro-ecological zones of Nigeria. The general sim of the study was to assess the spatial pattern of soil organic carbon in water-stable aggregate fractions in continuously cultivated croplands on various parent materials in Southern Nigeria using ordinary kriging interpolation techniques. The aim of this study is to carry out the assessment of soil organic carbon spatial pattern in water-stable aggregate fractions (>2.00 mm, 1.00 -2.00 mm, 0.50 -1.00 mm, 0.25- 0.50 mm, <025

mm) in continuously cultivated croplands on various parent materials, southern Nigeria.

2.0 Material and Methods

2.1 Description of the study Area

Geographically, southern Nigeria refers to the area bounded within latitudes 10°28' North of the equator and longitude 5°25' and 8°51' East of the Greenwich Meridian, occupying a land area of about 282,672.48 km² or about 30.6% of the total land area of Nigeria. It represents about 75.02 million or 39.3 % of the population of Nigeria (Monanu, 1975; and Ofomata, 1975) (Fig 1).

Figure 1: Georeferenced Map of the Study Area showing Sampling Locations

There are six major geological materials from which the soils of southern Nigeria are derived from. Namely: alluvium, coastal plain sands of Benin formation; upper coal

measures of Nsukka formation; sandstones of Ajali formation, lower coal measures of many formation; shale of Bende Ameki formation and Imo clay shale of Imo formation (Jungerius, 1964, Lekwa and Oparaugo, 1984; Ojanuga, 1977 and Igwe *et al.*, 2005). The soil type of the study area are dominantly ultisols (USDA Classification) or Acrisols (FAO/UNESCO Classification) (Lekwa and Whiteside, 1986; Igwe *et al.*, 1995; Okpamen *et al.*, 2013; Nuga, 2009 and Ahaiwe *et al.*, 2010).

The freshwater swamp and the tropical rainforest area have bimodal rainfall distribution pattern but with less intensity and clear distribution between wet and dry seasons in the tropical rainforest (Imo and Abia States). The fresh water swamp and tropical rainforest have average rainfall of 2500mm and 2350mm respectively (NIMET, 2018 and NDBDA, 2019). Air temperatures in southern Nigeria are generally high all year round. The mean maximum temperature of the area is 32°C while the mean minimum is 21°C, given an annual range of about 11°C. February and March are usually the hottest months, while July and September records the lowest temperature (Enwezor *et al.*, 1990; NIMET, 2017 and Ofomata, 1975).

Table 1: Sample Sites Under Different Parent Materials and Arable Croplands at the Selected Research Institutions and River Basin Development Authorities across the study area

Parent material	Soil Unit No	Soil Sample Site	Land Utilization type	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation (Masl)
CPS-FRIN-Isieke	FRN-01	Arable Cropland	Cassava/Maize/telferia mixed crop	05°25'00"N	07°31'34"E	162
	FRN-02	Arable Cropland	Cassava/Maize/telferia mixed crop	05°25'31"N	07°31'15"E	162
	FRN-03	Arable Cropland	Cassava/Maize/telferia mixed crop	05°24'49"N	07°31'50"E	173
SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe	NIH-04	Arable Cropland	Cassava/Maize/Melon Mixed Crop	05°49'21"N	07°18'24"E	177
	NIH-05	Arable Cropland	Cassava/Maize/Melon Mixed Crop	05°42'36"N	07°18'40"E	172
	NIH-06	Arable Cropland	Cassava/Maize/Melon Mixed Crop	05°51'59"N	07°18'40"E	171
ICS-AIRBDA Agbala	AIB-07	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/Okra mixed crop	05°17'40"N	07°05'42"E	110
	AIB-08	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/Okra mixed crop	05°18'01"N	07°05'50"E	98
	AIB-09	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/Okra mixed crop	05°18'12"N	07°05'28"E	10
CPS-NDBDA-Kpong	NDB-10	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/yam mixed crop	04°40'13"N	07°05'42"E	30
	NDB-11	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/yam mixed crop	04°40'08"N	07°05'50"E	30
	NDB-12	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/yam mixed crop	04°40'42"N	07°05'28"E	26
ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo	NDB-13	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/Telferia mixed crop	05°28'17"N	06°00'10"E	25
	NDB-14	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/Telferia mixed crop	05°28'05"N	05°59'55"E	17
	NDB-15	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/Telferia mixed crop	05°28'00"N	05°59'40"E	22

The study area is endowed with an annual average daily sunshine of 6.25 hours ranging from 3.5 hours at the coastal area and 9.0 hours at the far northern boundary. Their minimum and maximum hours of sunshine amount to 0.1 and 9.9 hours respectively (Uguru *et al.*, 2011, NIMET, 2008 and Odurukwe *et al.*, 1995). Similarly, it has annual daily solar radiation of about 2.25Kwh/m²/day varying between 3.5Kwh/m²/day at the coastal area and 7.0Kwh/m²/day at the northern boundary (NIMET, 2008 and Abia State official Gazette, 1992). Relative humidity over southern Nigeria ranges from 65% to 92% at the coastal area (Rivers and Delta States) through 82% at the central area (Abia and Imo States) to 95% toward the north (Enugu and Ogoja) areas (NIMET, 2008 and 2017). Evaporation is generally high in southern Nigeria because of the relatively high value of isolation and temperature (NIMET, 2008 and 2017).

The vegetation of the experimental area is typical of tropical rainforest vegetation. The secondary bush which dominates the area are the remnant of the typical rainforests which are fast disappearing in the area, some of the forest species found in the area especially in the alley crop portion include, oil bean (*Pentaclethra marcophyllum*), oil palm (*Elaeis guinensis*), plantain/banana (*Musa* spp), raffia palm (*Raphia* spp). Grasses and brown leaf weeds that dominate the entire area include *Panicum maximum*, *Pennisetum purperium*, *Aspilia*

africana etc. The major tuber and root crops mostly grown on ridges and mounds in the area include cassava (*Manihot esculanta*), yam (*Discorea* spp), sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas*) and cocoyam (*Xanthosomanas sagottofolium*), maize (*Zea mays* L) melon (*Citrullus vulgaris*) and vegetables such as okra (*Hisbiscus esculentus*) and *Fluted pumpkin* (*Telferia* spp). There were longer stand rotation in the horticultural and managed forest tree plantations. There were also mulching in the horticultural plants and prunings in the managed forestry tree plantations.

2.2 Field Studies and Sample Collection

Stratified random sampling as modified by Smith (1976), was used in the field. Soil samples were collected at 5 sites within 5 locations under four (4) LUTs. Soil samples were collected at the following locations: Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN), Isieke; National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT), Okigwe and Niger Delta Basin Development Authority (NDBDA), Isiokolo; Niger Delta Basin Development Authority (NDBDA), Kpong and Anambra-Imo River Basin Development Authority (AIRBDA), Agbala. The LUTs are shown in (Table 1).

A global positioning system (GPS) was used to locate each sampling point to generate their area and coordinates for further geostatistical soil spatial analysis (ordinary kriging). Three mini-pits (0.5 m x 0.5 m x 1 m) were dug in each of

the sample sites. A total of 15 soil samples were collected from geo-referenced point of 0-100cm sampling depth from each sample point for chemical analysis. Additional 15 samples were collected at each depth for the determination of bulk density. In general, 30 soil samples were collected.

2.3 Bulk density

Bulk density measurement was obtained by the cylindrical core method as described by Blacke and Hantge (1986), which was used to calculate soil organic carbon (SOC) on an area basis.

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{\text{Mass of oven dry soil (g)}}{\text{Volume of bulk soil (cm}^3\text{)}} \dots \dots (1)$$

2.4 Organic carbon content

Soil organic carbon content of the whole soil and that associated with the various water-stable aggregate fractions were quantified by Walkley and Black wet oxidation method as described by Nelson and Sommers (1982).

2.5 Spatial Analysis

Spatial analysis using GIS analysis was carried out in the Cartographic/GIS laboratory of the Department of geography and environmental management, university of Port-Harcourt, Rivers state, Nigeria. Ordinary kriging (OK) method was used in ArcGIS 10.1 environment to describe the spatial structures of the spatial maps of the SOC concentration in WSA (Ibe, 2021). Five (5) predictive spatial maps were

generated using best fit semi-variogram with ordinary kriging. The generated predictive maps were used to describe the spatial variability of soil organic carbon content for the continuously cultivated croplands at 0-100cm depth. The OK interpolation method was used for prediction of the values of the un-sampled locations X_0 by assuming the $Z^*(X_0)$ equals the sum of the known measured value (field measured value). Kriging process was calculated by the following equation (Wang, 1999).

$$Z^*(X_0) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_{iz} (x_i) \dots \dots (2)$$

Where: $Z^*(X_0)$ = predicted value at position X_0 ,
 $Z(x_i)$ = known value at sampling site X_i

λ_i = weighting coefficient of the measured site
 n = The number of sites within the neighbourhood searched for interpolation.

Semivariograms were used as the basic tool to examine the spatial distribution structure of the soil organic carbon content. Based on the regionalized variable theory and its intrinsic hypotheses (Neslen and Wendroh, 2003), a semivariogram is expressed as:

$$Y(h) = \frac{1}{2N(h)} \sum_{i=1}^{N(h)} [Z(x_i) - Z(x_i + h)]^2 \dots \dots (3)$$

Where: $Y(h)$ = Semivariance, h = Lag distance,
 Z = parameter of the soil property; $N(h)$ = number of pairs of locations separated by a lag distance h ; $Z(x_i)$ and $Z(x_i + h)$ = values of Z at position X_i and $X_i + h$ (Wang and Shao, 2013).

The empirical semivariograms obtained from the data were fitted by theoretical semivariogram models to produce geostatistical

parameters, including nugget variance (Co), structure variance (Ci), sill variance (Co + Ci), and distance parameter (λ). The nugget/sill ratio, $Co/(Co + Ci)$, was calculated to characterize the spatial dependency of the values. In general, a nugget/sill ratio <25% indicates strong spatial dependency and >75% indicates weak spatial dependency; otherwise, the spatial dependency is moderate (Cambardella *et al.*, 1994).

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 SOC content (g/Kg) in water-stable aggregate size fractions

Mean values of SOC content in water-stable aggregate size fractions across the study area are presented in Table 3: In > 2.00 mm WSA, soils

of ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo with CCC-CMTI had significantly ($p < 0.005$) higher SOC content (40.16 g/Kg), followed by CPS-NDBDA-Kpong under CCC-CMY (38.62 g/Kg). Whereas, SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe under CCC-CMM had the least (34.04 g/Kg). For 1.00- 2.00 mm WSA, there was significant influence of parent material and crop combination on SOC content with ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo having highest value (45.18 g/Kg), followed by ICS-AIRBDA-Agbala under CCC-CMO (37.44 g/Kg) and CPS-NDBDA-Kpong under CCC-CMY sequestered the least (33.60 g/Kg). In 0.50 -1.00 mm WSA, soils of ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo under CCC-CMTI had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher SOC content (46.10 g/Kg), followed by ICS-AIRBDA-Agbala under CCC-CMO (43.03 g/Kg), the least being CPS-NDBDA-Kpong under CCC-CMY (40.28 g/Kg).

Table 2: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Comparing SOC Content ($g\ kg^{-1}$) in Water-Stable Aggregate Size Fractions under Different Parent materials and Continuously Cultivated Croplands in the Study Area

Water-Stable Aggregate Fraction (mmm)	CPS-FRW-Isieke CCC-CMTF	SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe CCC-CMM	ICS-AIRBDA-AGBAK CCC-CMO	CPS-NDBDA-Kpong CCC-CMY	ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo CCC-CMTI	LSD	Significance
72.00	30.53 ^e	34.04 ^d	35.99 ^c	38.62 ^b	40.16 ^a	0.39	*
1.00 -2.00	36.80 ^c	34.99 ^d	37.44 ^b	33.60 ^e	45.18 ^a	0.74	*
0.50 – 1.00	42.77 ^c	41.88 ^d	43.03 ^b	40.28 ^e	46.10 ^a	3.15	**
0.25 -0.50	48.35 ^d	66.10 ^a	50.22 ^c	43.48 ^e	58.90 ^b	6.99	**
<0.25	41.80 ^e	46.30 ^c	63.06 ^a	45.71 ^d	47.66 ^b	12.33	**

Key = *, **= significant at 0.01 and 0.05 alpha levels respectively. Values in the same row followed by the same letter are not significant at 0.01 and 0.05 alpha.

CPS-FRW-Isieke = Coastal plain sands of Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Isieke, CCC-CMTF = continuously cultivated cropland of Cassava/Maize/Telferia in inter crop MFRW, SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe = shale of National Horticultural Research Institute, Okigwe CCC-CMM = continuously cultivated cropland of Cassava/Maize/Melon intercrop, ICS-AIRBDA = Agbala = Imo clay shale of Anambra-Imo-River basin Development Authority, Agbala, CCC-CMO = continuously cultivated cropland of Cassava/Maize/Okra intercrop, CPS-NDBDA-Kpong = Coastal plain sands of Niger Delta Basin Development Authority, Kpong, CCC-CMY= Continuously cultivated cropland of Cassava/Maize/Yam Intercrop, ALU-NDBDA – Isiokolo = Alluvium of Niger Delta Basin Development Authority, Isiokolo, CCC-CMTI = Continuously cultivated cropland of Cassava/Maize/Felijania intercrop in Isiokolo.

3.2 Geostatistical Parameters of the Fitted Semi Variogram for SOC Content in Soils of the Study Area

Geostatistical parameters of the fitted semi-variogram exponential model for SOC content are shown in Table 4. Maps showing the spatial distribution of the estimated SOC content in water-stable aggregate fractions in soils under different parent materials and varying crop combinations were the main output of the spatial analysis (Figs 2-6). The shaded different grey tone was according to the value estimated at those locations. The maps are shaded proportionally to the kriging results.

The semi-variogram parameters of SOC content explained the semi variance in the best way with the nugget values range 0.061-0.409. The nugget-sill ratio (N:S) ranged from 0.685-

0.1135. This hinted a strong spatial dependence of SOC content in WSA fractions and suggests that structural factors such as parent materials, climate, mineralogy, texture and slope are the primary cause of spatial patterns of SOC content in WSA. This is in agreement with Liu *et al.* (2004) and ECOS (2008), who noted that carbon sequestration is dependent on mineralogy, climate and slope. The fitted model occurs at a very short range, indicating localized dependency of SOC under different parent materials and arable croplands. The different ranges of the spatial dependence among the water-stable aggregate size fractions may be attributed to differences in response to the varying parent materials and crop combinations. Research findings in confirmation to this abound in literature (Schulin, 2013; Saygn *et. al.* 2017; Ibe, 2021).

Table 3: Geostatistical Parameters of the Fitted Semivariogram Exponential Model for SOC Content in WSA Fractions in the Study Area

Soil Property	Depth (Cm)	Nugget (Co)	Sill (Co + C)	Range (M)	(N:S)	R ²	ME	RMSE
SOC (gkg ⁻¹) in WSA fraction								
> 2.00mm	0-100	0.399	4.830	19.3	0.0825	0.663	0.0232	0.341
1.00-2.00mm	0-100	0.349	4.561	20.5	0.0765	0.633	0.00481	0.427
0.50-1.00mm	0-100	0.409	3.612	20.2	0.1135	0.661	0.00387	0.338
0.25-0.050mm	0-100	0.061	0.886	19.6	0.0685	0.701	0.00327	0.449
< 0.25mm	0-100	0.076	1.067	19.8	0.0715	0.684	0.024114	0.372

Key: R² = Coefficient of determination, RMSE = Root mean square error, , N:S= nugget-sill ratio, ME = Mean error

3.3 Spatial pattern of SOC content in water-stable aggregate size fractions at varying parent materials

The predictive maps showing spatial pattern of SOC content in the WSA fractions (> 2.00, 0-100-2.00, 0.50-1.00; 0.25-0.50, and <0.25 mm) under varying parent materials and arable croplands is shown in Fig 2-6. In the >2.00 mm WSA fraction, the results showed highest concentration of SOC in the northwest region of the study area. This correspond to soils developed under alluvium, cultivated with cassava/maize/telferia. Extreme southeast region dominated by coastal plain sands and shale with cassava/maize/okra and cassava/maize/yam croplands had minimum values of SOC concentration. The central southeast region had medium values of SOC content with mean error and RMSE of 0.232 and 0.341 respectively.

Figure 2: Spatial Pattern of SOC Content (gkg⁻¹) in >2.00 mm WSA Fraction

The predictive map of SOC content for 1.00-2.00 mm WSA fraction across the study area

(Fig. 3), showed highest concentration of SOC in extreme and central western zones of the study area. These represent the soils formed under alluvium and cultivated with cassava/maize/telferia crop combination. The extreme southeast region had minimum values. This area corresponds to soils formed under coastal plain sands, with cassava/maize/yam cropland. The central region and the northeastern corner of the study area had medium values of SOC with mean error and RMSE of 0.00481 and 0.427, respectively. These areas corresponds to soils developed under shale, Imo clay shale and alluvium cultivated with crop combination of cassava/maize/melon, cassava/maize/okra and cassava/maize/telferia respectively.

Figure 3: Spatial Pattern of SOC (gkg⁻¹) in 1.00-2.00mm WSA Fraction

The predictive spatial map of SOC in 0.5-1.00mm WSA fraction across the study area (Fig. 4), showed pockets of highest

concentration of SOC in WSA fraction 0.50-1.00mm, in the central southeast and western regions of the study area. These area represent soils developed under Imo clay shale, coastal plain sands and alluvium, cultivated with cassava/maize/okra, cassava/maize/yam and cassava/maize/telferia cropping combinations. The central southeast and northeast had medium values of SOC content. These area correspond to soils developed under shale, coastal plain sands and alluvium cultivated with cassava/maize/melon, cassava/maize/yam and cassava/maize/telferia with mean error and RMSE of 0.00387 and 0.338, respectively.

Figure 4: Spatial Pattern of SOC (gkg^{-1}) in 0.50-1.00 mm WSA Fraction

The predictive spatial map of SOC in 0.25-0.50 mm WSA fraction (Fig.3), showed pockets of highest values of SOC content in the Western Zone. There were also pockets of highest concentration of SOC in central southeastern corner of the study area. That corresponds to

soils formed under coastal plain sands and alluvium cropped with cassava/maize/telferia and cassava/maize/yam. There were pockets of minimum values of SOC in the northeastern region and extreme southern part of the study area. These areas represent soils developed under shale, coastal plain sands and alluvium, cropped with cassava/maize/yam, cassava/maize/melon and cassava/maize/telferia. Northern, central and southern regions had medium values of SOC concentration with mean error and RMSE values of 0.00327 and 0.449, respectively.

Figure 5: Spatial Pattern of SOC Content (gkg^{-1}) in 0.25-0.50 mm WSA Fraction

The predictive spatial map of SOC in <0.25 mm WSA fraction (Fig.3), showed highest concentration of SOC in the central and extreme western region of the study area. These corresponds to soils formed under alluvium and cassava/maize/telferia crop combination. Northeast and southern zones had minimum

values of SOC content. These represent soils developed under shale and coastal plain sands, cultivated with cassava/maize/melon and cassava/maize/yam. There were pockets of medium values of SOC concentration observed in the western and eastern zones. The area corresponds to soils developed under coastal plain sands and alluvium, cultivated with cassava/maize/telferia crop combination with mean error and RMSE of 0.0124 and 0.436, respectively.

Figure 6: Spatial Pattern of SOC Content (gkg^{-1}) in <0.25 mm WSA Fraction

4. Conclusion

Coefficient of determination (R^2) of SOC content in the various WSA fractions across the study area ranged from 0.851-0.701. The R^2 were > 0.5 , which indicate a good fit. The RMSE were approximately near to zero (0). This shows that the theoretical model was

adequate representation of the spatial patterns of SOC content.

The assessment suggests that the geographical allocation patterns of SOC content in the WSA fractions at 0-100 cm soil depths were extremely variable. The results suggest that both structural and stochastic factors influenced SOC content in the aggregate size fractions and suggest that structural factors (parent materials, climate, mineralogy, texture, and slope) are the primary cause of spatial patterns of SOC content in WSA fractions. These emphasize the significance of considering both parent materials and cultural practices (crop rotation, cropping combination, application of fertilizer and organic manure etc.) for sustainable soil management in the area. Application of organic manure should be encouraged in the study area. This will promote soil aggregation and C sequestration in macro- and micro- aggregate size fractions as this will enhance soil health and productivity, leading to sustainable ecosystem services and food security.

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